

TECHNISCHE
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WIEN

Dynamic City Livability Analysis

CLA24

Data Management Plan (DMP)

Lead partner:	TU Wien
Version:	1.0
Status:	Done
Dissemination level:	PU: Public
Document link:	https://github.com/lukasthekid/liveability-ex

Dynamic City Livability Analysis has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. .

Deliverable abstract

This deliverable is the initial Data Management Plan (DMP) for the Dynamic City Livability Analysis project, delivered in January 23. It will be kept updated as a living document. The DMP addresses the relevant aspects of the management of data and other outputs produced by the project according to the principles outlined in the FAIR data section.

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DELIVERY SLIP

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DOCUMENT LOG

Issue	Date	Comment	Author
1.0	04.04.2024	Initial commit	Lukas Burtscher

TERMINOLOGY

<https://eosc-portal.eu/glossary>

Acronym	Definition
DMP	Data Management Plan
CSV	Comma Separated Values
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	FAIR-Principles: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
MB	Megabyte
PDF	Portable Document Format
WP	Work Package

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1. Executive Summary

1.1. Introduction

A data management plan (DMP) is a structured document that keeps record of what research data is created or reused and what happens to that data during and after a project. It helps with planning the research process and defining responsibilities in a research project involving several researchers or institutions. For writing this DMP, we followed the [Horizon Europe DMP template](#).

Lukas Burtscher will act as the data manager who will be in charge of the actions described by this DMP.

1.2. Data Summary

- Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.
- What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?
- What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?
- What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?
- What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?
- To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?

The project will make use of existing datasets sourced from Kaggle and Livability reports, primarily in CSV format. This decision was made to leverage readily available data sources for analysis.

In terms of data generation, our project will primarily produce CSV files extracted from EIU livability report PDFs. Additionally, we'll create a series of images illustrating various plots derived during our data analysis. Crucially, a Jupyter notebook will be generated, housing all code, plots, and textual reports, facilitating transparency and reproducibility.

The purpose of this data generation and reuse aligns directly with the research objectives, aiming to address questions such as: how city quality of life rankings evolve over time, their interrelations, correlations with national statistics, cost of living, and the key determinants of city livability.

The expected size of the generated data will range between 12 KB and 5 MB, ensuring manageable file sizes suitable for storage and analysis.

Regarding data provenance, the generated data originates from EIU livability reports and is augmented by our analyses and visualizations.

In terms of data utility, our findings and insights are anticipated to be valuable not only to researchers but also to individuals contemplating relocation for work purposes and policymakers seeking comparative assessments of regional livability. This data could

inform decisions and policies aimed at improving urban quality of life and resource allocation.

Produced datasets (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10931591):

dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
P1	liveability-merc-2019.csv	Structured text	CSV	100 MB	no
P2	2021-eiu-liveability.csv	Structured text	CSV	100 MB	no
P3	liveability-eiu-2021-2.csv	Structured text	CSV	100 MB	no
P4	liveability-eiu-2019-2.csv	Structured text	CSV	100 MB	no
P5	Liveability-eiu-2019.csv	Structured text, Plain text	CSV	100 MB	no
P6	ex3.ipynb	Source code	CSV	100 MB	no

Reused datasets:

dataset ID	title	PID (e.g. DOI) or source	rights (e.g. license)	contains sensitive data
R1	Livability 2020 detailed	liveability-detailed-2020-teleport.org.csv	CC0: Public Domain	no
R2	Movehub City Rankings	https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/blitzr/movehub-city-rankings?select=movehubqualityoflife.csv	CC0: Public Domain	no
R3	Happiness Dataset 2015-19	https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/unsdsn/world-happiness	CC0: Public Domain	no

1.3. Methods and software used for data generation and reuse

The data sources are clearly identified as Economist Intelligence Unit (EIU) Reports and CSV datasets from Kaggle. The data was extracted and transformed into CSV files, a common and easily searchable format. The data, once transformed into CSV files, can be accessed and read using Python's pandas library. The code for this process is documented

in a Jupyter notebook. The use of CSV files and Python libraries like pandas and matplotlib ensures that the data and analysis are compatible with other systems. The transformations made to the data are based on specific research questions, indicating a structured approach to data analysis. The entire process, from data extraction to analysis, is documented in a Jupyter notebook. This allows for the results to be reproduced at any time, enhancing the reusability of both the data and the methodology.

1.4. Foreseeable research uses and /or users

Students and general public

2. FAIR data

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

- Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?
- Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.
- Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?
- Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?

We will make our data findable, by uploading it to a data repository that provides a persistent identifier, and adding relevant metadata. The repository will provide means for harvesting the metadata, including its machine-actionable representation.

The data is structured in a tabular format (like CSV) which is easily readable and interoperable. For versioning, we consider a version control system like Git. This allows us to track changes, handle multiple versions of the data and code, and enables others to reproduce specific versions of your work.

As there are no domain specific metadata standards applicable, we will provide a README file with an explanation of all values and terms used. This will help others to identify, discover and reuse our data.

Additionally, we will provide common metadata such as title, description, or keywords when publishing data. In this case, we will follow the default template provided by the repository, such as Data Cite Metadata or Dublin Core.

As far as possible, we will use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability.

2.2. Making data accessible

Repository:

- Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?
- Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?
- Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?

Data:

- Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.
- If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.
- Will the data be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol?
- If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?
- How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?
- Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?

Metadata:

- Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?
- How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?
- Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

We will make our data accessible by providing open access to data, wherever possible. In cases, where open access is not possible, we will provide meaningful metadata plus contact information for access requests. All the data is stored in a GitHub repository, which is licensed with MIT.

dataset ID	access conditions	restrictions / embargo reasons	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
P1	Open		2021-11-22	GitHub	10.5281/zenodo.10931591	CC-BY-4.0
P2	Open		2021-11-22	GitHub	10.5281/zenodo.10931591	CC-BY-4.0

dataset ID	access conditions	restrictions / embargo reasons	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
P3	Open		2021-11-22	GitHub	10.5281/zenodo.10931591	CC-BY-4.0
P4	Open		2021-11-22	GitHub	10.5281/zenodo.10931591	CC-BY-4.0
P5	Open		2021-11-22	GitHub	10.5281/zenodo.10931591	CC-BY-4.0
P6	Open		2021-11-22	GitHub	10.5281/zenodo.10931591	CC-BY-4.0

Repository description:

GitHub is the best place to share code with friends, co-workers, classmates, and complete strangers. Over three million people use GitHub to build amazing things together. With the collaborative features of GitHub.com, our desktop and mobile apps, and GitHub Enterprise, it has never been easier for individuals and teams to write better code, faster. Originally founded by Tom Preston-Werner, Chris Wanstrath, and PJ Hyett to simplify sharing code, GitHub has grown into the largest code host in the world. <https://github.com/lukasthekid/liveability-ex>

Methods or software needed to access and use data:

Python 3.10: This is the programming language you're using. It can be downloaded and installed from the official Python website.

Jupyter Notebook: This is the environment where you're running your code. It can be installed via pip (pip install notebook) or with Anaconda.

Required Libraries: Any Python libraries that your notebook uses, such as pandas and matplotlib as mentioned in your project. These can be installed via pip (e.g., pip install pandas matplotlib). Data Files: The CSV files that your notebook uses. These should be in the same directory as your notebook or in a place where your notebook can access them.

GitHub Repository: If the data and Jupyter notebook are stored in a GitHub repository, the person will need to clone this repository to their local machine. An IDE or a text editor: To view and edit the .ipynb files, tools like Jupyter, PyCharm, or even text editors like Sublime Text or Visual Studio Code can be used.

2.3. Making data interoperable

- What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?
- In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow re-using, refining, or extending them?
- Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?

We will make our data interoperable by providing and describing data in a way that is common within our domain. As far as possible, we will use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability. We will provide good documentation for all our datasets.

To ensure interoperability and facilitate data exchange and reuse, the project will adhere to widely accepted data and metadata standards such as CSV (for data storage), JSON (for metadata), and README files (for data description). These formats are commonly understood across disciplines and are easily accessible and parseable.

In the event that project-specific ontologies or vocabularies are used, mappings to more commonly used ontologies will be provided whenever feasible. This will enhance the understandability and interoperability of the data across disciplines.

The project's data will include qualified references to other data sources, such as datasets from previous research or supplementary data generated within the project. These references will be clearly documented within the metadata accompanying the datasets.

2.4. Increase data re-use

- How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?
- Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?
- Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?
- Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?
- Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.
- Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security and ethical aspects.

We will make our data reusable by adding metadata and comprehensive Readme files to all published datasets. The descriptions will include details on the methodology used, analytical, and procedural information. In case of publication, licenses for code and data will always be assigned and clearly marked. The digital research data obtained will be published Open Access under a Creative Commons CC BY license, provided there are no data protection concerns.

Our Jupyter notebook serves as a form of documentation, detailing the steps of the analysis. We make sure to include clear explanations and comments in the code. Our README file provides an overview of your project, the data, and the analysis steps.

The following data quality checks will be done: repeated samples or measurements, standardised data capture, peer review of data, and representation with controlled vocabularies.

3. Other research outputs

- In addition to the management of data, beneficiaries should also consider and plan for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout their projects. Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.).
- Beneficiaries should consider which of the questions pertaining to FAIR data above, can apply to the management of other research outputs, and should strive to provide sufficient detail on how their research outputs will be managed and shared, or made available for re-use, in line with the FAIR principles.

...

4. Allocation of resources

- What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.)?
- How will these be covered? Note that costs related to research data/output management are eligible as part of the Horizon Europe grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions)
- Who will be responsible for data management in your project?
- How will long term preservation be ensured? Discuss the necessary resources to accomplish this (costs and potential value, who decides and how, what data will be kept and for how long)?

There are no costs dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR.

Cost name	Cost type	Description	Unit	Value
Estimated total costs				0

The data manager will direct the data management process overall, with Lukas Burtscher being responsible for ensuring metadata production, day-to-day cross-checks, back-up and other quality control activities are maintained. The researchers will be responsible for routine supervision of the dataset development.

The GitHub repository for this project can be found at the following URL: <https://github.com/lukasthekid/liveability-ex>. The repository contains a directory named `data/`, which houses all the data used in this project. It should be noted that this directory contains more data than what is actually utilized in the Project Jupyter Notebook.

The data is organized into subdirectories, each of which is named according to the type of data collection it represents. For instance, all datasets that describe the happiness of a population in a country are located in the `Happiness-data` subdirectory.

The CSV files containing the data are stored within these subdirectories. The source code associated with this project has been registered with a Digital Object Identifier (DOI), specifically [10.5281/zenodo.10931591](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10931591).

5. Data security

- What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?
- Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?

5.1. Storage and backup facilities

For the duration of the project, storage and backup of data will be ensured by the project manager.

5.2. Data security and protection of sensitive data

We pay strict attention to compliance with the relevant institutional and national data protection policies.

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any sensitive data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.

Access to data during research:

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
P1	reading only	reading only	reading only
P2	reading only	reading only	reading only
P3	reading only	reading only	reading only
P4	reading only	reading only	reading only
P5	reading only	reading only	reading only
P6	writing	writing	reading only
R1	reading only	reading only	reading only
R2	reading only	reading only	reading only
R3	reading only	reading only	reading only

All incidents will be handled individually by an incident response team that is maintaining the affected service.

5.3. Long-term preservation and deletion of data

dataset ID	location for long-term storage	minimum retention period (≥ 10 years)
P1	GitHub	10 years
P2	GitHub	10 years
P3	GitHub	10 years
P4	GitHub	10 years
P5	GitHub	10 years
P6	GitHub	10 years

6. Ethical and legal issues

- Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).
- Will informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

6.1. Personal data

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any personal data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.

6.2. Intellectual property rights and ownership

There are no legal restrictions on the processing and disclosure of our data.

6.3. Ethical issues

No particular ethical issue is foreseen with the data to be used or produced by the project. This section will be updated if issues arise.

7. Other issues

- Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)?